

METHODOLOGY OF EDUCATION IN THE NATIONAL- SPIRITUAL SPIRIT BY TEACHING UZBEK FOLK SONGS IN EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: This article contains insights about how important and effective music culture lessons are in the future of the young generation. In addition, it is emphasized that imparting knowledge of the national spirit in music culture classes of secondary schools is one of the main methods of awakening love for the motherland in the minds of students.

Key words: knowledge, culture, music and art, methodology, students, potential, future, motherland.

Introduction:

In the following years, the work of developing and strengthening the spiritual culture of our people rose to the level of important state policy. The promotion of the idea of "New Uzbekistan in 2021" by the Honorable President Sh. Mirziyoev, the issue of using Uzbek folk songs, which are considered an integral part of the national music art, became very important in educating young students in many ways. Celebrating the spiritual traditions of the population and ancient holidays, organizing the international "Eastern Songs", "International Status Festival", "International Bakhshi-Poet Epic Festival", "International Cinematography" and other music festivals and conferences, all of which are music, including The Uzbek people demand to accelerate the search for new forms in the field of music. The rise of creative forces in our republic is reflected in the creativity of students.

The rise of creative forces in our republic is reflected in the creativity of students. "We are the children of Uzbekistan", "Borderless beauty" contests, "City of Masters", "Laughter of ancient narratives", singer contests dedicated to famous hafiz and composers Haji Abdulaziz Abdurasulov, Jorakhan Sultanov, Maomurjon Uzokov, Komiljon Otaniyozov are important in the development of aesthetic education of the young generation. is becoming important.

Learning Uzbek folk songs means respect and benevolence to representatives of different nationalities and people with different opinions, recognition of the uniqueness of different religions and other cultures, and appreciation of the values of different peoples and social groups. In the formation of this idea, various forms and methods of educational work such as learning the traditions and customs, culture, national-musical heritage of other peoples, forming concepts of international friendship can be widely used. In particular, the song festival "Uzbekistan - My Country" held in our Republic since 1996 aimed to ensure the unity of different peoples. The formation of singing skills of students is the most important tool while educating students in the national-spiritual spirit based on Uzbek folk songs. As the students perform the song, positive emotions such as excitement, joy, cheerfulness, dynamism, Motherland, national pride, humanitarianism, and patriotism are formed. In the song, two aesthetic tools - music and artistic words - come together. Therefore, group singing

in the hands of an experienced teacher serves as an important tool in educating students in the national-spiritual spirit.

This competition is held in order to create new songs that praise our creative, open-hearted, benevolent people, and urge people of different backgrounds and nationalities to preserve the sacred soil of the homeland and independence as the apple of their eye. Examinations were held in two stages from March 10 to May 1 of every year among students of general education schools, extracurricular educational institutions, higher education institutions, teachers-educators and pupils of "Mehribonlik" houses and boarding schools based on the recommendations of institutions and individual executives. However, in the later periods, such competitions were directed to spiritual and enlightening works, such as selection of works of art created at a high artistic level in different languages in the genres of status performance, choral performance, academic performance, folklore performance, vocal instrument performance, and their use in youth education.

Azerbaijani folk song "Zabul tesnisi" about the cultural heritage of the brotherly and foreign nations; "Happy Girls Song" Kyrgyz folk song; "Atush" Uighur song; L.V.Beethoven's "Heroism" (3rd symphony); "Mazurka" by Chopin; "Trout" by Schubert, music by D. Omonullaev, "Our Children of Turkestan" with a poem by T. Mullaboev; Music by T. Azimov, with a poem by P. Momin "Taraldi - shodiyona"; music by I. Hamroev, "Pakhtazorga parvonalar" with a poem by Yo. Mirzo; "Polka" by M. Glinka, "Naples" by P. Tchaikovsky, "Oromijon" reworked by R. Gubaydullin, musical like the Uzbek folk tune The works promote the ideas of unity, peace and harmony with their different ideological content, thoughts, views and goals.

We used the following musical pieces in the training sessions to develop the idea of inter-ethnic harmony among the students:

A) About the mutual equality of nations:

1. Music by L. Mujdaboeva, Qambar Ota's poem "My Uzbekistan".
2. Music by N. Norkhojaev, poem by P. Momin "Keng Turkistan".

B) About international cooperation:

1. Music by F.Alimov, poem by P.Momin "Ahillik - dostlik".
2. Music by S. Yudakov, poem by A. Mukhtar "Soul of Uzbekistan".

B) Respecting other nations:

1. Music by D.Zokirov, poem by M.Qoriev "Song of Friendship".
2. Music by K.Kenjaev, poetry by Q.Mahammadi, Sh.Yormatov Worked in "Youth Ways"

G) About openness to cultures of different peoples and nations:

7. "As time goes by." Indian folk song.
8. "Dawn". Arab folk song.
9. "Goldfish". Japanese folk song.
10. "Nairez". Tajik folk song.
11. "O Tajikistonim" music by N. Qurbanasaev, poem by Kh. Jorayev.

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experienced teacher serves as an important tool in educating students in the national-spiritual spirit. Songs on the topics of Motherland, independence, our country, nature, work, and childhood were included in the "Music Culture" program. These songs serve as an important tool in educating students to love the Motherland, loyalty to its future, hard work, and aesthetic education. In the process of teaching singing, developing an emotional attitude to the learned song, developing imagination, musical hearing and memory, understanding the importance of musical means of expression, singing in sonorous, strong, light sounds, being able to listen to oneself and one's friends, singing with and without accompaniment, harmonically by singing in two or three voices. it is planned to carry out tasks such as the formation of hearing ability.

When the teacher chooses a song to sing, first of all, he carefully analyzes the artistic value, content, educational value, and image range of the work. Depending on the result, he chooses the methods of teaching the song.

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